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Severity of Failure: Resilience Assessment on the Shop Floor

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Abstract

Shop floor operations are affected by uncertainties and disruptions. These can come from the supply chain causing shortages of materials, worker unavailability due to, e.g., unforeseen pandemics, and spontaneous machine breakdowns. To address these challenges, resilient manufacturing systems are essential. However, there is a lack of practical methods for quantifying how well a shop floor withstands and recovers from such disruptions and assessing its level of resilience. Therefore, we propose a new approach for evaluating the resilience of the shop floor by assessing the production schedule and its underlying scheduler. Our Severity of Failure (SoF) method assesses each scheduled task by calculating the impact of its failure on the entire production schedule and combining it with the probability of the failure occurring. The method has been validated by assessing production schedules generated by various dispatching rules, demonstrating both its practical applicability and its potential to evaluate the resilience of different scheduling algorithms. Furthermore, the beneficial effect of buffer times on resilience was also evaluated.

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1. Introduction

The modern manufacturing landscape is increasingly complex and interconnected, characterized by rapid advancements in technology, globalization, and ever-evolving consumer demands [1]. As industries strive to optimize production processes for efficiency and cost-effectiveness, they often encounter a significant challenge: the vulnerability of highly optimized systems to disruptions and uncertainties. These disruptions can range from minor machine malfunctions and worker unavailability to major global crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, geopolitical conflicts, supply chain bottlenecks, or uncertainties caused by inflation and increased costs [2]. The consequences of these challenges impact shop floor operations.

As industries integrate more automated and interconnected systems, the failure of a single machine can have cascading effects throughout the entire production process, potentially leading to extensive downtime, increased maintenance costs, and reduced overall system efficiency [3]. Without a clear understanding and measurement of shop floor-level resilience, manufacturers may be unable to implement effective strategies to prevent or mitigate these disruptions. This can result in frequent and prolonged production halts, lower product quality, and ul-

timately loss of competitive advantage in an increasingly dynamic market [4].

In the context of modern manufacturing, resilience is increasingly recognized as a critical property of production systems. Resilience in manufacturing refers to the ability of a production system to anticipate, prepare for, respond to and recover from disruptions without interrupting operations or minimizing their impact [5].

While resilience shares similarities with concepts like robustness and reliability, it is distinct in several key ways. Reliability refers to the probability that a system or component will perform its required functions under stated conditions for a specified period of time [6]. It emphasizes the avoidance of failure but does not account for recovery or adaptation after a failure occurs [4]. Robustness, on the other hand, is the ability of a system to maintain its operational performance despite the presence of disturbances or variations in conditions [6]. It focuses on the system's resistance to disruptions but typically assumes a static response to such challenges [4]. Resilience, however, encompasses both the anticipation of potential failures and the capacity to respond dynamically to them [3, 4]. It not only includes the ability to absorb shocks and continue operations (as in robustness) but also incorporates the capability to recover quickly and adapt to new conditions post-disruption [3, 6]. This

means that while a robust system is being proactive, a resilient system is reactive. Resilience, therefore, extends beyond mere robustness or reliability by addressing the system's ability to recover from failure and return back to its initial state leveraging properties such as redundancy, flexibility, and adaptability [3].

In the context of highly integrated cyber-physical systems, where the failure of a single component can affect the entire production process, resilience becomes an essential quality which needs to be assessed [4]. Understanding the effect a failure of a specific task can have on the entire production schedule is crucial for preserving production continuity, making it a key focus for evaluating resilience.

In order to strengthen the resilience of a manufacturing system with targeted measures, it is necessary to be able to assess and quantify the level of resilience - both the baseline before implementation and the system's response after the measure is applied. This is essential to ensure the right measures are selected and that their effectiveness is verified. Therefore, production managers need tools to evaluate the resilience of the shop floor accurately.

In this article, we present a method to assess shop floor resilience by evaluating both the production schedule and the corresponding scheduler, providing a key performance indicator (KPI) for resilience. By analyzing not only the schedule but also the scheduler's dynamic response, we can measure resilience itself, rather than static characteristics like robustness or risk.

Although several methods have been published, we found that most are not practically suited for assessing resilience on the shop floor. Current limitations we found include vague conceptual frameworks, lack of practical applicability, and limited relevance to the shop floor. Most importantly, existing methods often fail to incorporate the manufacturing system's dynamic response to disruptions, which is essential for accurately measuring resilience. Our Severity of Failure (SoF) method addresses these limitations by providing clear calculation instructions, tailoring the approach specifically to the shop floor, and including the system's response to disruptions

The main idea is, that every disturbance of the shop floor ultimately impacts individual tasks. Whether due to machine failure, worker unavailability, or missing materials, it is always a task that cannot be executed. Therefore, each task represents a potential point of failure within the manufacturing system of the shop floor. Our method evaluates each task based on its individual severity of failing in the overall production schedule, taking into account the probability of a failure occurring and calculating an average with all tasks.

The main contribution of this work is a novel method with clear calculation instructions specifically tailored to the assessment of resilience on the shop floor. The SoF method intends to support further research on the integration of resilience into production scheduling by enabling the evaluation of different strategies and thus advancing resilience research in manufacturing environments.

2. Related Work

2.1. Classification of Resilience Measures

Hosseini et al. [4] categorizes resilience assessment methodologies into two main categories: qualitative and quantitative. The qualitative category covers methods to evaluate system resilience without depending on numerical KPIs and can be further broken down into (i) conceptual frameworks that offer best practice guidelines and (ii) semi-quantitative indices which provide expert evaluations of various resilience qualities. In contrast, the quantitative methods include (i) general resilience approaches that provide domain-independent metrics applicable across domains to quantify resilience and (ii) structural-based modeling approaches that represent resilience components through domain-specific modeling. They further divide the general measures into (i) probabilistic and (ii) deterministic approaches, while the structural-based models are categorized into (i) optimization, (ii) simulation and (iii) fuzzy logic models.

Cheng et al. [7] argue that there is no uniform metric for quantifying resilience, which makes it difficult to compare resilience across different systems. Therefore, the authors divided the quantitative metrics as functions of the following indicators: (i) Length of hazard and recovery periods, where the recovery is a stochastic process (ii) Performance over a time period, where performance loss and recovery are evaluated (iii) Performance at a time instant, instead of over a period (iv) Probabilistic metrics, are based on the random occurrence of disturbances and the random performance deterioration.

We categorize the SoF method within the category (i) length of hazard and recovery periods. Cheng et al. [7] argue that methods in this category typically do not include the exact magnitude of performance loss and recovery, and the estimation of the expected recovery period is difficult in practice. Our method manages to overcome these limitations by providing a specific assessment of the performance loss and recovery.

2.2. Resilience Assessment Methods

Various resilience assessment methods already exist for different use cases and at varying levels of detail. While the general topic of resilience is extensively researched, most studies focus primarily on the supply chain level and the overall manufacturing system, with several review papers already available (e.g., [2, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12]).

In contrast, resilience in the context of production systems on the shop floor - particularly assessment methods - remains little researched [13]. Existing methods in this area are often vague, as quantifying the recovery ability of systems proves to be a challenging task. A good representative selection of related publications are the following:

Chryssolouris and Lee [14], Chryssolouris [15] and Alexopoulos et al. [16], proposed the penalty of change (POC) method as a measure of resilience, which calculates the expected cost of a potential change due to a disruption. For each

potential change, the cost of this change is multiplied by the probability of its disruption occurring.

Bruneau et al. [17] and Zobel et al. [18] introduced the Resilience Triangle to visualize and measure the performance loss and recovery over time following a disruption. The area under the triangle represents the resilience loss, where a larger area indicates more significant performance degradation and slower recovery. The main metrics from this model are: Time to Recovery (TTR): The time required for a system to return to its pre-disruption performance level. Resilience Loss: The area under the curve between the initial disruption and the point of recovery, quantifying the size of the expected degradation in performance over time.

Gu et al. [19] highlight two key resilience metrics to analyze multi-stage serial-parallel manufacturing systems with unreliable machines and finite intermediate buffers: the Throughput Settling Time (TST) and the Overtime to Recover (OTTR). TST measures the time required for a production system to stabilize its throughput after a disruption, while OTTR quantifies the additional overtime needed to compensate for lost production. These metrics provide insights into how quickly and efficiently a system recovers from disruptions. Systems with lower TST and OTTR values are more resilient, as they return to normal operation faster and with minimal resource costs. By applying these metrics, manufacturers can assess the impact of different system configurations, such as machine redundancy, buffer capacities, and reallocation of tasks on overall system resilience. For instance, increasing buffer capacities or adding parallel machines may reduce both TST and OTTR. Gu et al. [19] emphasize that resilient systems are those capable of minimizing downtime and resource expenditure during recovery, making these metrics crucial for optimizing production system performance.

Rose [20] proposes a resilience metric which is bound between 0 and 1. This provides a convenient interpretation of resilience since 0 corresponds to no impact of the disruption and 1 to the worst degraded performance. His metric forms a ratio between the difference of the expected system performance to the non-disrupted performance and the difference of the worst-case system performance to the non-disrupted performance. Determining the expected and the worst system performance could be difficult in practice.

2.3. Resilience in scheduling

In their review of resilient scheduling, Zhang et al. [21] identified that current research predominantly centers on the application of reinforcement learning. This approach facilitates real-time adaptations to production schedules with the primary aim of reducing makespan and tardiness. Furthermore, the training of such models is frequently enhanced by integrating stochastic elements that represent uncertainty.

3. Severity of Failure (SoF) Method

The main limitation we identified in existing methods for assessing resilience on the shop floor is that most are not specifically tailored to this context and often provide only a general concept without detailed instructions. They typically lack modeling for expected future system performance, fail to quantify recovery ability or rely solely on historical data. Our method addresses these limitations by offering clear and practical guidelines for resilience assessment specifically designed for the shop floor, although the underlying principles can be applied to other areas as well.

Our method is based on the concept that every planned task represents a potential point of failure or disruption, with the assumption that only one failure occurs per sufficiently short period of time. Consequently, each task is assessed for its probability of failure and the impact that its failure would have on the overall production plan. This approach uses the Mean Time Between Failure (MTBF) to determine the probability of failure for each machine and the Mean Time To Repair (MTTR) in combination with rescheduling to estimate the severity of each task failing. This allows us to assess not only the schedule itself but, more importantly, the resilience of the underlying scheduling process.

The SoF method follows three steps:

1. Calculate the binomial failure probability for each machine
2. Calculate the severity of each individual scheduled task failing
3. Calculate the overall Severity of Failure for the schedule and scheduler

3.1. Binomial failure probability for each machine

Since a failure can occur at any time on any machine, independently from each other, failures follow a binomial distribution. The binomial failure probability P_{fail} for each machine m is calculated based on the machine's $MTBF$ and the number of tasks n assigned to that machine within a specific time frame T in the schedule. The binomial distribution models the number of failures across a fixed number of independent Bernoulli trials, where each trial has the same probability. In this context, we consider the reliability of each machine over a defined period. The probability of a machine failing within this time frame is calculated using the following formula:

$$P_{fail,m}(MTBF, T, n) = \binom{n}{1} \frac{T}{MTBF} \left(1 - \frac{T}{MTBF}\right)^{n-1} \quad (1)$$

3.2. Severity of failure for each task

Each task in the scheduled solution could fail, therefore each of these tasks will be considered as a possible point of failure.

To calculate the severity of a specific task's failure, the failed task is first replaced with a repair period equal to the machine's MTTR.

With the use of a chosen *scheduler object*, the remaining tasks (including the failed task) are being rescheduled with consideration of the repair time on that machine. This process generates a new schedule with an updated makespan time $t_{failure}$, see Figure 1a) and 1b).

The new makespan $t_{failure}$ is then min-max normalized between the original makespan $t_{evaluation}$ and the worst possible makespan $t_{failure,worst}$, and is subsequently multiplied by the binomial failure probability of the respective machine $P_{fail,m}$. The worst makespan time $t_{failure,worst}$ is calculated by leaving the schedule as is but moving it forward in time by the repair time, i.e., the production stands still until the repair is finished, see Figure 1c). Normalization ensures a Severity of Failure (SoF) value of 0 if the rescheduled tasks yield the same makespan as the original schedule, indicating that the task's failure has no impact on the overall makespan.

Algorithm 1 Severity of Failure for each task

for each task i in schedule do

1. Replace task with repair period (MTTR)
2. Reschedule remaining tasks → scheduler object
→ new makespan time $t_{failure}$
3. Calculate severity of this task failing:

$$S_i = \frac{t_{failure} - t_{evaluation}}{t_{failure,worst} - t_{evaluation}} \times P_{fail,m} \quad (2)$$

end for

3.3. Overall Severity of Failure

To obtain the overall SoF value for the entire schedule and the corresponding scheduler, the mean of all individual SoF_i values across each tasks is calculated, where k represents the total number of tasks:

$$SoF = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=0}^k SoF_i \quad (3)$$

4. Results

To test our method, we applied the SoF method to schedules produced by different schedulers, thereby we are able to assess the schedule as well as the corresponding scheduler for resilience. To produce the schedules, we used several different datasets of orders and for the scheduler object, we used a variety of popular dispatching rules. Additionally we investigated the effect of buffer times on the resilience.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the algorithm.

4.1. Dataset

The datasets contain various entities relevant to the manufacturing process. The structure of the datasets, reduced to the relevant attributes, is illustrated in Fig. 2. In these datasets, all steps have the same priority, but individual steps can only be performed on a specific set of *appropriate machines* and have varying machining times depending on the machine's *performance factor*. Therefore it is considered a flexible job shop problem. In total 14 different datasets were tested, with the amount of tasks to be scheduled ranging from 10 to 400 on 9 different machines, having a scheduling periods of under a week.

4.2. Scheduler

This method is generally applicable for assessing *any* scheduler. In this paper we tested the method on several popular dispatching rules, evaluating their ability to schedule tasks in a resilient manner. The tested dispatching rules are:

- *First In First Out (FIFO)*: Jobs are processed in the order they arrive.
- *Shortest Processing Time (SPT)*: Jobs with the shortest processing times are prioritized.
- *Longest Processing Time (LPT)*: Jobs with the longest processing times are prioritized.
- *Earliest Due Date (EDD)*: Jobs with the closest due dates are prioritized.
- *Critical Ratio (CR)*: Jobs are prioritized based on urgency relative to remaining processing time.

Fig. 2. Relevant entities and attributes of the manufacturing dataset.

Additionally, to investigate the impact of buffer times on resilience, we also enabled the schedulers to add buffer times of varying length after each task.

4.3. Findings

We found that the length of the schedule, or the size of the data set, has no influence on the SoF, since only the difference of makespan is considered. While the tested dispatching rules exhibited a similar order of magnitude in their SoF values, the ranking of the dispatching rules varied across different dataset sizes. Consequently, a definitive ranking of dispatching rules based on resilience could not be established. Furthermore, no correlation between dataset size and SoF was observed.

Fig. 3. Severity of Failure (SoF) values for different dispatching rules over buffer duration with a dataset of 367 tasks

It could be clearly observed, that with increasing buffer time, the SoF decreased and therefore the resilience increased. The behavior of the SoF for different dispatching rules over varying buffer duration for an exemplary dataset can be seen in Figure 3.

5. Discussion

The Severity of Failure (SoF) method enables the assessment of resilience on the shop floor, allowing the evaluation of selected measures (e.g., buffer times) and their impact on resilience. It also enables the integration of resilience aspects into production scheduling.

By identifying the tasks with the highest SoF, the shop floor manager can direct attention to these critical tasks. This proac-

tive approach enables managers to be better prepared for potential disruptions

By incorporating the scheduler into our method, rather than just the schedule, we are able to assess resilience more comprehensively. This approach models the system's dynamic and reactive behavior, rather than just its robustness.

The length of the schedule and amount of tasks have no influence on the SoF method.

It is important to note that when using dispatching rules as schedulers, the rescheduling in the method is minimal. This is because the scheduling is based on queuing tasks, meaning the order of jobs remains largely unchanged.

The results of this study highlight the benefiting effect of buffer times on resilience, since the extra time leaves room for the repair and rescheduling of tasks. On the other hand, it should be considered that this, in turn, increases the makespan and thus reduces the throughput leading to more expensive products. However, also the cost of unexpected disturbances should not be neglected. Therefore, our method should serve as a stepping stone for future research in the area of intelligent buffer management, balancing cost and resilience, so that future schedulers based on e.g. reinforcement learning, have the ability to optimize towards resilience.

A significant limitation of this method is its reliance on the selected scheduler object for computational efficiency. In our experiments, we used computationally inexpensive dispatching rules, which have a complexity of $O(n \log n)$, where n denotes the count of jobs or tasks to be scheduled. Computationally expensive techniques are therefore inefficient as they require scheduling n -times.

6. Conclusion

In this work, we present a novel method for assessing the resilience of the shop floor by evaluating both the production schedule and its underlying scheduler. By tailoring the method specifically to the shop floor and providing clear calculation instructions, we ensure its practical applicability.

Consequently, the implementation within actual manufacturing environments is easily achievable, as it merely requires access to the production schedule and the corresponding scheduling algorithm.

Incorporating the scheduler object enables the evaluation of the dynamic and reactive behavior during rescheduling, allowing for a true assessment of resilience rather than just robustness. We tested our method using various dispatching rules and

multiple datasets of orders. Our results show that the Severity of Failure (SoF) is more influenced by the dataset than by a ranking between dispatching rules.

Additionally, we evaluated the impact of buffer times and demonstrated that they are a crucial factor in enhancing resilience on the shop floor.

Future research should focus on integrating the SoF method into reinforcement learning or other adaptive algorithms to enable intelligent scheduling decisions that balance resilience and efficiency.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

References

- [1] A. Mukherjee, P. Ruediger-Flore, A. Billimoria, D. Chittari, W. Mustafa, M. Klar, M. Glatt, M. Kloft, J. C. Aurich, Training a Machine Learning Model for representing Manufacturing Systems towards optimizing Resilience, *Procedia CIRP* 120 (2023) 768–773. doi:10.1016/J.PROCIR.2023.09.073.
- [2] D. S. Fowler, G. Epiphaniou, M. D. Higgins, C. Maple, Aspects of resilience for smart manufacturing systems, *Strategic Change* 32 (6) (2023) 183–193. doi:10.1002/JSC.2555.
- [3] A. E. Elhabashy, S. El-Breshy, H. Fors, A. Harfoush, Resiliency of Manufacturing Systems in the Industry 4.0 Era – A Bibliometric Analysis, *Proceedings of the International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management* 11 (1) (2021) 4879–4886. doi:10.46254/AN11.20210844.
- [4] S. Hosseini, K. Barker, J. E. Ramirez-Marquez, A review of definitions and measures of system resilience, *Reliability Engineering & System Safety* 145 (2016) 47–61. doi:10.1016/J.RESS.2015.08.006.
- [5] D. Bauer, M. Böhm, T. Bauernhansl, A. Sauer, Increased resilience for manufacturing systems in supply networks through data-based turbulence mitigation, *Production Engineering* 15 (3-4) (2021) 385–395. doi:10.1007/S11740-021-01036-4/FIGURES/6.
- [6] A. L. Sambowo, A. Hidayatno, Resilience Index Development for the Manufacturing Industry based on Robustness, Resourcefulness, Redundancy, and Rapidity, *International Journal of Technology* 12 (6) (2021) 1177–1186. doi:10.14716/IJTECH.V12I6.5229.
- [7] Y. Cheng, E. A. Elsayed, Z. Huang, Systems resilience assessments: a review, framework and metrics, *International Journal of Production Research* 60 (2) (2022) 595–622. doi:10.1080/00207543.2021.1971789.
- [8] B. R. Tukamuhabwa, M. Stevenson, J. Busby, M. Zorzini, Supply chain resilience: definition, review and theoretical foundations for further study, *International Journal of Production Research* 53 (18) (2015) 5592–5623. doi:10.1080/00207543.2015.1037934.
- [9] S. Y. Ponomarov, M. C. Holcomb, Understanding the concept of supply chain resilience, *The International Journal of Logistics Management* 20 (1) (2009) 124–143. doi:10.1108/09574090910954873/FULL/HTML.
- [10] D. Ivanov, A. Dolgui, Viability of intertwined supply networks: extending the supply chain resilience angles towards survivability. A position paper motivated by COVID-19 outbreak, *International Journal of Production Research* 58 (10) (2020) 2904–2915. doi:10.1080/00207543.2020.1750727.
- [11] M. Negri, E. Cagno, C. Colicchia, J. Sarkis, Integrating sustainability and resilience in the supply chain: A systematic literature review and a research agenda, *Business Strategy and the Environment* 30 (7) (2021) 2858–2886. doi:10.1002/BSE.2776.
- [12] K. Katsaliaki, P. Galetsi, S. Kumar, Supply chain disruptions and resilience: a major review and future research agenda, *Annals of Operations Research* 2021 319:1 319 (1) (2021) 965–1002. doi:10.1007/S10479-020-03912-1.
- [13] L. Sielaff, D. Lucke, T. Adolf, A. Friedmann, Resilience Metrics for Production Systems, *WT Werkstattstechnik* 113 (6) (2023) 266–270. doi:10.37544/1436-4980-2023-06-58.
- [14] G. Chryssolouris, M. Lee, An Assessment of Flexibility in Manufacturing Systems., *Manufacturing Review* 5 (2) (1992) 105–116.
- [15] G. Chryssolouris, *Manufacturing Systems: Theory and Practice*, Vol. 2, Springer-Verlag, 2006. doi:10.1007/0-387-28431-1.
- [16] K. Alexopoulos, I. Anagiannis, N. Nikolakis, G. Chryssolouris, A quantitative approach to resilience in manufacturing systems, *International Journal of Production Research* 60 (24) (2022) 7178–7193. doi:10.1080/00207543.2021.2018519.
- [17] M. Bruneau, S. E. Chang, R. T. Eguchi, G. C. Lee, T. D. O'Rourke, A. M. Reinhorn, M. Shinozuka, K. Tierney, W. A. Wallace, D. Von Winterfeldt, A Framework to Quantitatively Assess and Enhance the Seismic Resilience of Communities, *Earthquake Spectra* 19 (4) (2003) 733–752. doi:10.1193/1.1623497.
- [18] C. W. Zobel, Representing perceived tradeoffs in defining disaster resilience, *Decision Support Systems* 50 (2) (2011) 394–403. doi:10.1016/J.DSS.2010.10.001.
- [19] X. Gu, X. Jin, J. Ni, Resilience Measures of Manufacturing Systems Under Disruptions, *ASME 2014 International Manufacturing Science and Engineering Conference, MSEC 2014 Collocated with the JSME 2014 International Conference on Materials and Processing and the 42nd North American Manufacturing Research Conference* 1 (10 2014). doi:10.1115/MSEC2014-4047.
- [20] A. Rose, Economic resilience to natural and man-made disasters: Multidisciplinary origins and contextual dimensions, *Environmental Hazards* 7 (4) (2007) 383–398. doi:10.1016/J.ENVHAZ.2007.10.001.
- [21] C. Zhang, M. Juraschek, C. Herrmann, Deep reinforcement learning-based dynamic scheduling for resilient and sustainable manufacturing: A systematic review, *Journal of Manufacturing Systems* 77 (2024) 962–989. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmsy.2024.10.026. URL https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S027861252400253X